

I have a cock on yonder hill I keep
him for a wonder
And every time the cock do crow,
It lightens, hails and thunders. – *A gun* [6]

These four riddles contains a particularly neat example of an extended metaphor. Extended metaphors are metaphors developed through more than one point of comparison: 'And every time the cock do crow, / It lightens, hails and thunders.' This riddle compares the firing of a gun to a cock that produces lightning (the flash), hail (bullets) and thunder (the report) when it crows.

What has teeth but cannot eat? – *A saw*.

What has a tongue and can't talk?
– *A shoe*.

Many eyes and never a nose, one
tongue, and about it goes. – *A shoe*.

In these riddles we find the metaphorical extension or comparisons. They are based on metaphor.

There is something with a heart in
its head. – *A peach*

This example is built on the comparison of various physical features of a peach to anatomical structures of an animal. [5]

These riddles represent indisputable metaphorical riddles. In each some quality of a specific object is compared to a similar quality of a different object. Metaphorical riddles are irreplaceable in the development of thinking:

“The little red cock runs along the
neck” – *Fire*

Solving such riddles is deciphering metaphors. Penetrating into the hidden meaning of the metaphor, the guesser must compare, compare objects or phenomena from different, often distant areas, see features of similarity in them, highlight them, refer them to one semantic category and, on the basis of this, determine what was conceived, solve a logical problem. Solving metaphorical riddles develops both figurative and logical thinking.

Riddles are a genre in which ambiguity is acceptable at all levels of language. They favour metaphors the purpose of which is both to mislead the listener and to bring to light a new aspect of a thing, an object or an action that is as a rule highly familiar to all. They demonstrate that two linguistic categories that are from one perspective different are in fact similar when viewed in another light.

Riddle metaphors cannot be forced into a single scheme by comparing them unequivocally to the metaphors of, say, spoken or poetic language. The scale of expression in riddles is a wide one, ranging from creative invention often improvised on the spot via extremely worn or commonplace metaphors to images the meaning of which has become completely obscure.

Analysing metaphors has not been easy for researchers, even though metaphor is the vital feature of riddles. Models have been developed for determining the structure of riddles and the metaphors used in them, but they often use only a small corpus of material, and attempts have then been made to fit the model to the classification of larger materials.

Metaphor is a general property of poetry. Furthermore, its incidence and complexity are more evident in the riddles than any other poetic genre. [1]

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THE PLACE OF ABBREVIATION IN MEDIA DISCOURSE

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МЕСТО АББРЕВИАТУРЫ В МЕДИАДИСКУРСЕ

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Abstract

The difference between “discourse analysis”, “speech acts” and “text linguistics” is clarified by referring to the studies carried out in this field. The attention is drawn to different tendencies related to the topic. The article

also deals with the mass media and its types. Importance and the special role of abbreviations in media is analyzed in the example of English-language newspapers.

Аннотация

Различие между «дискурсивным анализом», «речевыми актами» и «лингвистикой текста» уточняется при обращении к исследованиям, проводимым в этой области. Обращается внимание на различные тенденции, связанные с данной темой. В статье также рассматриваются средства массовой информации и их виды. На примере англоязычных газет анализируется значение и особая роль аббревиатур в СМИ.

Keywords: discourse analysis, speech acts, text linguistics, abbreviation, media discourse

Ключевые слова: дискурсивный анализ, речевые акты, лингвистика текста, аббревиатура, медиадискурс.

One of the most complex and controversial concepts in modern linguistics is the concept of "discourse". In the early days of its emergence and place in the scientific literature, the discourse was equated with the text. That is, "discourse" and "text" are used in the same sense. As media discourse is the main plot of this study, it is necessary to give general information about the concept and define media discourse.

A. Abdullayev shows that in the early 80s of the last century, attempts were made to differentiate text and discourse, and two tendencies were observed in this approach. The first tendency is based on independent concepts of text and discourse, and the second tendency is based on their connection [1, p.181]. In the process of further development of text linguistics and discourse analysis, these two concepts have been differentiated. Currently, there is a lot of research on the study of discourse. However, there are many definitions of discourse, and many of them have a different approach to the concept. In linguistics, rather than the definition of discourse, there are controversial points and different approaches to its study. The study of media discourse generally requires that approaches to discourse analysis be directed in a single direction. Discourse is both a process and a result of this process. Discourse is a view of reality in different discursive practices and the regulation of this view [4]. It is important to expand this explanation, which has a relatively complex and abstract effect. When defining a discourse, researchers always return to the text-discourse relationship. *"Discourse is a broader concept than a text. Discourse is both a process of linguistic activity and its result, and the result is the text itself"* [7, p.307]. A. Kibrik's definition overlaps the first part of M. Foucault's comment. The difference here is that the end result is the transformation of discourse into text. Such discursive activity leads to the creation of a certain text.

A. Mammadov shows that *"the discourse is perceived as a part of the conversation "in action" in front of the text. It acquires a certain meaning in context. This context is used by the transmitter of information in a language for specific purposes in a specific context and meaning. Discourse is a connected part of speech"* [9, p.58].

The idea of identifying speech acts with discourse is based on the theory of speech acts and directives, commissions, assertives, emotions, etc. based on the definition of speech acts [2; 6; 10]. A speech act or speech acts are imagined to be smaller than a text due to the amount. However, this opinion cannot be accepted as the reality. The main feature of speech acts is

their tendency to dialogic speech. We must not forget that monologue is also an act of speech. The text is formed as a collection of speech acts. The revival of each act of speech partially reveals its interaction with extralinguistic factors. Discourse is an active conversation. This activity is not limited to the act of reciting or writing a speech act. Involvement of speech material in discursive activity activates it. Discourse is created for a specific purpose, and its creator is the speaker as well as the listener. The action of discursive requires two sides. The purpose of its creation also depends on these aspects. The speaker has his own communicative goals, and the listener has his own communicative goals. While transmitting the information, the basic knowledge of the transmitter and the receiver do not coincide. Both sides filter the information, comprehend, interpret and evaluate it as they understand it.

The speaker and the listener are the participants in a discursive activity. This mentioned process is the simplest discursive activity. If we approach the issue from a broader perspective, the addressee can represent a specific audience. However, this does not exclude the existence of the addressee's own audience. Each period and culture has its own audience. Moreover, the concept of a special audience is used. H. Perelman wrote that the speaker influenced a special audience with his own ideas, facts and arguments [3, p.19]. The audience is the majority of the audience imagined by the speaker. For a writer, if this audience is made up of his readers, critics, and colleagues, the readership that the journalist envisions or imagines is wider, and that audience depends on the emerging topic and the problem. If the writer forms an artistic discourse, the journalist is the creator and participant of the media discourse. Thus, the discourse is divided into types according to the audience to which it is addressed. One of the most important and widespread types of discourse is media discourse.

The process of presenting and interpreting facts in a media discourse is separate from those facts. The presentation and interpretation of facts are not an expression of objective truth. Because here the presenter, the commentator has his own or dictated position to him. Each audience has its own attitude to the facts. The wider the audience exists, the more differentiated forms of this relationship appear. Communication with a specific audience has its own rules, forms and types. These forms and types arose in the process of long-term experience and were distinguished from each other by certain features and characteristics. The audience demands

the discourse they want. If the discourse is not presented, then the audience does not accept it and does not join the discursive activity. The choice of viewers of television programs depends on this aspect. If the audience does not like the program of a particular presenter, he does not participate in the discourse presented by him, he changes the channel, and thus the discourse also changes. From this point of view, a characteristic feature of modern media discourse is that the speaker has a conditional agreement with the audience. Of course, the speaker does not have to agree with the addressees and the audience in advance. It is important that the audience is interested in the information addressed to the addressee, as well as his style of presentation. Reality is formed on the basis of general opinion. If the addressee can create his own audience, he does not lose his status. Otherwise, he will have to give his place to someone else.

Media discourse has a wide scope. This is due to the large number of topics, as well as the size of the audience. Therefore, media discourses are divided into genres and subgroups.

The mass media is also diverse. Newspapers, magazines, radio, television, Internet sites are the objects of media discourses. Newspaper materials, television and radio materials, as well as materials on websites differ from each other. Radio audio, television have the power of visual impact. Newspapers and magazines are static, with articles published in them tending the reader to comment and interpret, evaluate, and analyze. Informative materials in all media, to be more precise, news and innovations are similar and have the same genre. News, innovative media discourses are directly proportional to the efficiency of information, the interests of the audience. The Internet, with its ability to update news and updates frequently, increases the interest in following the information spread there. However, it should be considered that all other media outlets are now able to achieve equality by creating their own websites, Facebook and Instagram in the real life, and continue to compete.

One of the main goals of the media is to convey new information to readers as quickly, concisely and figuratively as possible. In this case, the issue of verbalization of information by graphic, descriptive, linguistic means must be skillfully addressed. The value of information also depends on the reaction to it. However, it is about ensuring speed, innovation and clarity in the transmission of information. Speed requires the economical use of language tools, the elimination of redundancy, and the avoidance of repetition. In this regard, abbreviations play a special role in the language of the media, first of all, they allow the compression of the language used. The press is one of the means of language development and enrichment, ensuring the constant functioning of the language in the public and mass spheres. New words and expressions appear and spread in the language of the press. The press demonstrates the level of development and use of language, the tendencies that occur in it. Newspapers and magazines are the main means of recording new words in the language. At the same time, on the basis of materials published in the press, the possibilities and frequencies of language

tools can be determined. The rapid dissemination of information requires less language outlets to be used in its verbalization. The first major role of the abbreviation in the media discourse is to help the realization in the principle of economy. Abbreviations are quite short from the full form they replaced as a unit of re-nomination. Phrases consisting of two, three or more components can be replaced by one word via the help of abbreviations. Words that contain long graphemes or phonemes that are longer than the average word depth of the language are abbreviated and optimized. *"Newspapers and magazines are the most efficient means of recording new words and phrases and providing them for application. Compared to other genres of written speech, they react immediately to the occasions in all spheres of public life, and serve as a source of recording new words that may be included in the general lexical layer"* [8, p. 26].

In modern times, each country has its own mass media, and newspapers have a special place among these mass media outlets. At present, newspapers are also distributed via the Internet. Almost every newspaper has its own website. As English is a global language in the world, the number of newspapers in English is quite large. The United Kingdom and the United States are at the forefront of newspapers and the press. Both British and American English-language newspapers are distributed around the world, and their publications are published in many countries.

The history of the British press dates back to the 16th century. In 1588, "English Mercury" was published. One of the predecessors of the British press is the "News book". In 1851, Reuters, the largest news agency in Europe, opened in Britain. In Britain, daily 200 newspapers and weekly 1300 magazines are published and distributed. The BBC distribution agency was founded in 1922. Newspapers for the general public in the United Kingdom can be divided into two groups. The first group is called quality paper (broadsheets), and the second group is called popular press (popular press, tabloids). "The Times", Britain's first significant newspaper, was published in 1785. The circulation of press was founded in Britain in 19th century, and the newspapers which would later become the country's most influential media. "The Financial Times" (1886), "The Guardian" (1821), "The Daily Telegraph" (1885), and "The Independent" (1886) had been published. Currently, the most popular British newspapers are: "The Times", "The Financial Times", "The Guardian", "The Daily Telegraph", "The Independent", "The Daily Mail", "The Mirror", "The Sun", "The Express".

The most popular English-language newspapers in America are "The New York Times", "The Wall Street Journal", "The Washington Post", "Los Angeles Times", "USA Today", "The Herald Tribune", "New York Post", "Houston Chronicle", "The Star Tribune", "Newsday", "The Chicago Tribune", and "The Boston Globe".

These British and American newspapers are daily newspapers and have a large volume and circulation.

Their pages are full of political, economic, social, scientific, cultural, in short, articles in almost all fields, and abbreviations are widely used in these articles.

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